

Foundations of early childhood education

Report: Torres Strait Islander people and Aboriginal epistemologies of the world

Introduction: What is meant by resilience?

According to Cronin, D'Arcy & Murphy, (2019) the meaning of resilience for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people refers to their ability to withstand, adapt and recover from any drastic changes to their living, culture and growth with time. To build resilience in Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people, one needs to understand their communities, their perspectives and narratives. In other words, this means understanding the epistemologies of these communities. Furthermore, these changes have been long called for by these communities. According to Atkinson, (2017), the Aboriginal communities of Victoria have been continuously asking early childhood practitioners to move beyond shallow and tokenistic inclusion of Aboriginal culture into the curriculum and develop a deeper understanding of the local communities, their philosophies and epistemologies (p.7). To further understand this, we shall explore the Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people epistemologies and then policy development around these epistemologies and suggestions for further improvement.

Aboriginal and Islanders epistemologies

- 1. Spiritual beliefs:** According to the "Possum skin pedagogy" by Atkinson, (2017), spirituality holds a very high value in Aboriginal communities, are quite sensitive and must be presented with a direct involvement of Aboriginal community leaders in presence (p.11). For both Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people, spirituality is present in their daily life and influences all major life practices and tasks, as stated by Bourke, et.all, (2022). This can be seen through narratives of journey and healing (traditional practices, practices of life and death, regeneration), narratives of ceremonies (emphasising on their welcoming and bidding farewell of skins {cloaks} eg. Welcoming a new member to the country with a skin {cloak}). To continue effective passing of spiritual traditions beliefs, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander

people believe in passing them down with a presence of an elder from the community, oral storytelling and rich use of language linked to movement in songs, rhymes and symbols which are special to these people. For younger children, this is passed by incorporating Dreamtime storytelling for children. According to Crocker, (2005), Dreamtime refers to the stories of ancestors of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people who came before and discovered the land, culture and spiritual realms and is expressed through unique art and images for children. As opposed to Western notions of passing information to children, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people are very firm about connecting children's learning with past, present and future through spirituality and build connection to their ancestors within the presence of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander elders as explained by Atkinson, (2017). Hughes, & Moore, (1997) say, "According to Aboriginal people, education for children must acknowledge their culture, spirituality and their identity within the culture" (p.11)

- 2. Interconnectedness - connections to country, people and land:** Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people believe that the world was created by their ancestral beings and that their spirits are present in the animals, beings, land and nature. Thus, a connection to the past, present and future is very important for them. According to Hughes, & Moore, (1997), as widely different from western notions of living and being, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander universe is basically free from any physical or scientific qualities as well as time and space (p.9). Rather their world takes meaning with their connection to the country, the people and relationships and the land (p.8). Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people believe that their ancestors and spiritual beings are still present on the same land as them in present times (p.9). This means for that Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people, looking at things like how people got everything they need from nature, how they developed their symbols and art with deep meanings and connections to their ancestors, how they are welcomed to the country and connect with it. For Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities, the importance of respecting the land, understanding the purpose and reusing every available resource; respecting the relationships with people and roles of individuals in the community; and notably preparing children for future by passing down the cultural and spiritual stories from their ancestors is noted in Groome, (1995). According to Gee, Et. al, (2014), concepts of indigenous land ownerships were quite different from European ways of ownerships. Aboriginal

people found the land to be a richly symbolic and spiritual landscape and not a physical landscape. Individuals who were part of groups, shared a spiritual connection and obligations with this land, or country, and thus, there was no concept of ownership of land for the communities.

- 3. Holistic understanding and connection to nature:** For Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people, their health and well-being is interweaved with their connection to the land, community and culture. Hughes, & Moore, (1997), in their work, talk about the importance of ceremonies and healing practices involved in Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities that are connected with spirituality and traditional ancestors' knowledge passed onto them. In another work by Atkinson, (2017), the author talks about the added richness of looking at the world around us and finding the use of nature to build things. She researched and connected with local Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities to understand that they look at people first, then their particular needs as a group and then go to nature to immediately find inspiration and answer to their needs. They believe in nature's role in the growth and development of human beings. This is widely different from the western ideas of healing and growth where body and mind are seen separate from nature and healing practices are far from spiritual connection but more based on science and technology (based on work by Smith, 2005). It understands the rights of Aboriginal and Torres Strait islander people in relation to their health and well-being being viewed as holistic encompassing mental, physical, spiritual, cultural health and interconnected with nature. According to Gee, Et. al, (2014) guiding principle, Crucially, if the harmony of this is interrupted, it will result in poor health and well-being of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people.

Policy development in last 20 years and recommendation

Let us look at some strategies and documents developed for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people's success and inclusion in the last 20 years.

Closing the gap - Strategy of 2008

According to Pholi, (2009), 'Closing the gap' strategy was created to acknowledge the resilience and ongoing strength of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people in 2008,

underpinned by the belief that Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people should have a genuine say in the policies, programs and services that affect them especially in healthcare, emplacement and family development. It was hugely based on the aims of overcoming the inequality experiences faced by Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people in the past and to support them in achieving successful life outcomes similar to those as all Australians. For children this meant providing equitable resources and opportunities for low socio-economic income families and to provide culturally relevant education accessible to them, as stated in Australian Government Department of Education [AGDE], 2024.

A key point to note here is that there were no separate bodies for devising such strategies for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people, rather these were constructed by Council of Australian Governments (COAG) based on their communication with local communities. In relevance to early childhood education and well-being, within this strategy, 6 closing the gaps targets focusing on child mortality, health, education, life expectancy, employment were introduced.

In 2014, a school attendance target was added, and in 2015, an expanded early childhood target was added, based on the data provided by Department of Families, Housing, Community Services and Indigenous Affairs (2009). This was done to undo the disadvantages done to the Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people in the fields of healthcare, childcare, family well-being and socio-economic sector.

Inclusion in learning frameworks and teaching practices - EYLF (2009 and new changes in 2022) and NQF (2012)

Early Years Learning Framework (EYLF) - In 2009, Commonwealth of Australia introduced a formal learning framework for use with children aged birth to 5 years old with a clear vision of children's growth and learning development, set principles, research backed educational goals and strategies for teachers to use in educational settings. The framework was developed to ensure that "All children have the best start in life to create a better future for themselves and the nation" (Commonwealth of Australia, 2009, p. 5). This statement puts forth the idea that Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander children are also included in the plans and strategies to ensure their success.

However the 2009 version of EYLF was not quite specific and reflective in terms of support for the indigenous communities of the country. It was in 2022 version 2 of EYLF, developed by the Australian Government Department of Education [AGDE] (2022) where

much more integrated and reflected practices were introduced. It is planned to be achieved through community involvement and culturally sensitive practices. According to AGDE, (2022) “The main differences you will see are a stronger connection between the frameworks and the National Quality Standard in areas such as sustainability, theoretical approaches, critical reflection, the importance of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander ways of being, knowing and doing, inclusion and the addition of three new principles”. This was done with clear research including surveys, literature reviews and stakeholder feedback over 2 years before the document release.

National Quality Framework (NQF) - In 2012, a system for regulating early childhood services and care was established known as the National Quality Framework (NQF). It was developed with a vision of providing a national approach to regulation, assessment and quality improvement for childcare educational organisations. Within this 6 principles and framework 7 quality areas were introduced. One of the principles of this document was that Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander cultures are valued. In the document, it mentions how important for childcare services and frameworks to work respectfully with indigenous communities, recognize that Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander cultures are the oldest and resilient cultures in the world, recognize the commitment to equality for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander in education, and that EYLF is one opportunity to work towards cultural security (Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, 2012).

National Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Education Strategy - 2015

The National Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Education Strategy recognised the first 5 years of a child's life as critical for long term health and well-being. It was built with 5 key goals and outcomes under the ‘Closing the gap’ agreement to empower Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander children and families and with a vision that all children within the communities are born healthy and strong with ongoing nurturing, according to AGDE, (2015).

See appendix 1 for National Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Education Strategy - Goals.

Source: Australian Government Department of Education [AGDE], 2015, *National Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Education Strategy*.

According to NIAA, 2024, “Connection to culture has been embedded throughout the Strategy as this is essential for young Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander children to thrive – to feel safe, loved, proud in their identity and able to fulfil their potential”.

National Indigenous Australian Agency - 2019

A national commonwealth body for indigenous communities called Nation Indigenous Australian Agency (NIAA) was created in 2019, with a vision that Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people are heard, recognised and empowered. This agency was structured in a way where they ensured that multiple perspectives were taken into account, professional integrity was maintained, investment in indigenous communities are made, and most importantly, the decision makers are strong partners (I.e indigenous communities and the government).

NIAA Stretch Reconciliation Action plan 2022-2025 (RAP)

According to the CEO of NIAA, Broun, (2022), NIAA Stretch Reconciliation Action plan 2022-2025 (RAP) is an official document devised to address and impact the reconciliation journey for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people. The action plan partners with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people in relation to devising and implementing strategies that will “affect the communities in and out of government, to ensure alignment of policy, strategies and investments towards achieving the best possible outcomes for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people” (NIAA, 2022, p.4).

Within this document, strategies have been developed for the upcoming years that shall be based on the 4 principles of **Reflect** (building relationships with the communities by ensuring staff and members of different organisations understand the importance of reconciliation and reflect on practices); **Innovate** (developing a clear vision for reconciliation within an organisation and developing plans and strategies to achieve the vision); **Stretch** (demonstrating reconciliation leadership by thoroughly including reconciliation strategies internally within an organisation’s business and working); and **Elevate** (upholding actively challenged initiatives within organisations to demonstrate commitment to RAP). Based on these principles, RAP supports different organisations around the country to continuously develop their commitments by choosing one principle and following the action plan with a structured approach and timeframe (NIAA, 2024).

Critical analysis and recommendation for improvement:

For the past years, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities have been urging policy developers and those involved with fostering education for their children to not merely use signs, symbols and indigenous tokens to acknowledge Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander epistemologies in practice (Atkinson, 2007, p.7). To avoid both cultural theft and sheer ignorance to the communities, Non indigenous people are urged to move beyond the shallow tokenism and to deeply understand the cultures and practices and embed them into practice.

Based on the the local voices of Aboriginal and Torres Strait communities (Atkinson, 2017), it is important to critically analyse all policies and procedures devised for Aboriginal and Torres Strait communities through this lense -

Are the policies built on Aboriginal and Torres Strait epistemologies? Are the procedures developed with Aboriginal and Torres Strait communities’ particular success in mind? What does “success” mean for Aboriginal and Torres Strait communities?

When asked, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people responded that they were looking for their children to be prepared to be Aborigines first, and then for wider world societies (as claimed by Hughes, & Moore, (1997)). This may be seen as what educational success may be perceived for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people, in comparison to western world view of “success”. To Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people, the perseverance of their culture, values and understanding of connections with people, places and beings may be a valuable knowledge as compared to western knowledge of mere reading and writing rhymes and stories.

The policies and procedures that are developed so far by the Australian government and separate bodies may have moved into supporting Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people to achieve success, however there has not been a clear indication of how these policies are creating way for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander children to learn “the traditional” ways of their culture. Surely, there has been ongoing improvement in policies with time, but these changes are still in the process of becoming “relatable” to Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people (Atkinson, 2017).

According to data collected by Atkinson (2017), Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people want these policies and procedures to be relatable to them, to their children, a program that “reflects” their lives (p.36). This means that they should be able to connect their lives, cultures and epistemologies to the visions and plans laid out for them by different ministries and educational bodies and stereotypical ways and being of Aboriginal and Torres Strait communities are not used.

For example: using an ideology from Aboriginal community for all communities around the area is not feasible. Rather connecting with each and every local community, understanding their idea of success and growth and then working towards it. Or simply understanding that learning is holistic for these indigenous communities, meaning that they feel a connection with their environment and their well-being is highly influenced by it. Here, pushing the idea of “western” ways of good well-being where a person’s well-being is not holistic rather is categorised into scientific ways, is not ideal.

[What is the recommended practice here? What can be done for the future?](#)

For the future, it is recommended to deeply understand what “success” means for each community, and how their understanding of success can be achieved. According to Atkinson (2007), educators and policy makers should sit with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander

elders and understand what they want their children to learn (p.13). This knowledge should build the foundation of visions and principles for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander.

Secondly, their connection to the land, country and nature needs to be deeply taken into account while making any policies and programs. This means looking at holistic ways of learning and well-being and keeping a firm notion in mind that Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people will struggle to thrive without their connection to land, nature and country. This does not mean incorporating a few visits to parks or setting up natural corner in early childhood settings, but to deeply investigate what nature taught these communities, how they made use of it to survive, how can one ground themselves to ensure their well-being and how this knowledge can be embedded throughout the program and educational settings rather than one tiny area (Atkinson, 2017).

Furthermore, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people's deep sense of spiritual connection to their ancestors is to be highly valued. In policies and programs, this can look like incorporating their beliefs into their well-being plan development, educational success. Furthermore, respecting what Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people might choose to share with us regarding their spiritual beliefs and values. According to Atkinson, (2017), Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people are still on the path to revive their culture and languages. Therefore they have the absolute right to choose if they want to share their journey with educators or not. Building a connection and reciprocal relationships with no expectations with local communities is highly recommended practice to ensure that the programs and policies are central to their beliefs and notions of "success".

Conclusion

In conclusion, the report focused on Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people epistemologies and world views. These were then noted in comparison to western worldviews and quite significant differences were observed. In another section of this report, relevant policies and frameworks for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people were analysed in relation to educational success. In the last section, critical analysis of what 'success' looks like to Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people and how these have been respected in the policies and frameworks have been noted. Lastly, the report suggests some recommendations and questions for people planning program and frameworks for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people.

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